

Millimeter-Wave Backscattering Channel Modelling for Sensing Applications in an Industrial Scenario

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Abstract—Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS) and radar-based detection in industrial scenarios face harsh propagation conditions, which pose challenges for designing and evaluating radio system performance. In this work, we introduce a wideband backscattering channel measurement campaign from 18 to 40 GHz in a machine room, using a quasi-monostatic antenna setup to scan the environment. Based on the experimental data, a Ray-Tracing (RT) tool is calibrated, and the Large Scale Parameters (LSPs) are analyzed. The measured and predicted data are then used to evaluate the performance of Radio Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) applications.

Index Terms—Channel Sounding, Ray-Tracing, Backscattering, Radio Simultaneous Localization (SLAM),

I. INTRODUCTION

In the rapid development of wireless technologies, improving connectivity, reducing latency, and supporting more device connections, the current vision of 6G marks a major transformation, expanding radio signals beyond communication to include sensing and environmental mapping. Joint Sensing and Communications (JSAC) will be crucial in the evolution of 6G, merging communication and sensing through high-frequency technologies [1], [2]. The sensing capabilities could be embedded at base-station but also into handheld devices, enabling them to map their surroundings and accurately position themselves without dedicated infrastructure. Currently, accurate Simultaneous Location and Mapping (SLAM) is achieved by incorporating laser-based radars (Lidars) or Visual-SLAM (V-SLAM) cameras [3]. The concept of Radio SLAM (R-SLAM) is to record the backscattered radio signals by beam scanning the environment and finely exploit the Multi Path Components (MPCs) to retrieve ranging and bearing information, and derive the maps of indoor spaces jointly with the self-localization [4], [5]. This application is of practical interest in industrial environments, where people, or Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) robots can move in complex metallic environments.

The radio channel characteristics in these scenarios have been investigated in several studies also producing a 3GPP channel model [6], and highlighting the importance of the dense components [7], [8]. Ray-tracing (RT) channel models are well suited for communication-oriented application, but the accuracy demand for a proper 3D modeling and calibration to provide accurate results [9]. Sensing oriented channel characterization and models are poorly investigated in literature [10] and demand for further studies. In [11] a first backscattering channel campaign at 60 GHz was realized in office and

corridor environment, providing a stochastic description of clusters according to the environment map.

In this paper we present a novel backscattering sensing-oriented channel campaign in industrial environment (Sec.II). This campaign addresses the 18-40 GHz band and allows a full polarimetric characterization of the channel. Going beyond previous work on the one-way single polarized radio channel, we validated a RT tool, allowing to reproduce the backscattering of the environment (Sec. III). Finally we introduce an exploitation of the channel model for R-SLAM applications.

II. BACKSCATTERING CHANNEL MEASUREMENT CAMPAIGN

A. Scenario Description

Measurements were performed in a machine room with dimensions of 35 m long, 16 m wide and 3.5 m high is considered in our industrial scenario. This industrial-type scenario contains sheet metal-covered ventilation shaft, metal cabinets and vertical metal pipes, as well as metal support columns. The exterior walls are sheet metal, the ceiling also contains metal rails and the floor is concrete. The antennas displace

Fig. 1: 3D representation of measured environment and RT simulation.

along a loop-shaped trajectory of 46 positions spaced at an average of 0.8 m apart. This allows a corridor-like situation to be explored initially, followed by a winding path between the machines and the outer walls of the room. The layout of the loop path and the plan of the room are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Each red square on the ground represents a measured position of the antennas. This picture also provides a 3D representation of the machine room, the corresponding material assignment, and some rays generated by the RT tool (Sec. III).

B. Channel Sounding Setup

Measurements were carried out with a 4-port Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) between 18 GHz and 40 GHz with a frequency step of 5 MHz. Two dual-polarized dual ports horn antennas are used to provide a quasi-monostatic polarimetric measurement of the industrial environment.

The antenna gain was measured beforehand in an anechoic chamber and the results are illustrated in Fig. 2. The red and the blue line corresponds to the two ports measurement for Vertical (V) and Horizontal (H) polarizations. The maximum gain changes linearly with the frequency from 15 to 21 dBi, and the cross-polarization level is below 25dB.

Fig. 2: Gain pattern of double polarized horn antennas at 18 GHz (a), 28 GHz (b), 40 GHz (c). Measurement (continuous line), expected (dots).

To scan the azimuth plane, an $x - y - \phi$ positioner is used to mechanically translate and steer the horns. The azimuth is scanned from -90° to 90° with an angular step of 5° . The configuration is automated using an external PC. The overall setup is shown in Fig. 3. The Tx/Rx antennas are moved to 46 positions within the scene. Each position of the sounder is manually referenced using a laser measurement of the distance from the walls or a fixed heavy machine in the room. At each position (out of 46), each frequency (out of 4400) and each antenna orientation (out of 36), the polarimetric channel is characterized by a 2×2 matrix:

$$\mathbf{H}(f) = \begin{pmatrix} H_{V,V}(f) & H_{V,H}(f) \\ H_{H,V}(f) & H_{H,H}(f) \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $H_{\zeta,\xi}(f)$ represents the channel transfer function for the (ζ, ξ) polarization combination (namely V or H). The

Fig. 3: Channel Measurement Setup

results are converted in time domain by the Inverse Fast Fourier Transform (IFFT) with 0-200 ns range and 0.045 ns resolution. The relative power of the Tx-Rx coupling is estimated within a 5 ns time window applied to all channel impulse responses at $-57 / -59 / -63 / -40$ dB for the VV / VH / HV / HH polarization, respectively.

III. RAY-TRACING MODELING AND CALIBRATION

Those measurements are compared to the predictions of the Volcano Flex RT model, which is configured with up to 2 reflections and 2 diffractions, and enables diffuse scattering components.

A. Ray Tracing Calibration

In previous work [9], we calibrated the environment for a single V polarization, using two distant antennas for communication applications. After calibration, ray-path powers include a -3 dB offset per reflection and a -2 dB offset per diffraction. Diffuse scattering was adjusted to maintain power balance between reflected and diffused components. The same RT tool is now used to evaluate the backscattering channel, with consideration of multiple polarization states. For comparison to the mono-static channel measurements presented in Sec.II, the RT simulations are first run with quasi-co-located isotropic dual-polar Tx and Rx antennas at the edge of the measured frequency band i.e., at 18 and 40 GHz. As a second step the measured radiation patterns (Fig.2) have been embedded, by considering the Angle of Departure (AoD) and Angle of Arrival (AoA) of each ray. Finally, the channel prediction is interpolated to any intermediate frequency, leading to the same channel transfer function as defined in Eq. (1).

The multi-polarimetric nature of both the measurements and predictions permit to complement the calibration of the RT model. The value of the cross-polar discrimination (XPD) can be adjusted via a calibration factor XPR_F , an offset XPR_O in dB, and the diffuse-scattering depolarization coefficient K_{xpol} , which was introduced in [12]. The power of a diffused ray-path is split into a co-polar and a cross-polar components with parameter K_{xpol} defined as the ratio between the cross-polar diffused power and the total diffused power.

The corrected cross-polar components $\hat{S}_{V,H}$ and $\hat{S}_{H,V}$ are obtained as follows:

$$\hat{S}_{V,H}^{dB} = S_{V,V}^{dB} - XPR_O + XPR_F \cdot 20 \cdot \log_{10}(|S_{V,H}| / |S_{V,V}|) \quad (2)$$

$$\hat{S}_{H,V}^{dB} = S_{H,H}^{dB} - XPR_O + XPR_F \cdot 20 \cdot \log_{10}(|S_{H,V}| / |S_{H,H}|) \quad (3)$$

where $S_{\zeta,\xi}(f)$ represents (ζ, ξ) component for each ray. The cross-polar discrimination (XPD) is key parameter for comparison between the dual-polar measurements and predictions. The discrimination between polarizations VH and VV is computed at each position by integrating the channel gains in all Tx/Rx steering angle ϕ_s and delay τ :

$$XPD^{dB} = 10 \cdot \log_{10}(\sum_{\phi_s} \sum_{\tau} |h_{VV}(\phi_s, \tau)|^2) - 10 \cdot \log_{10}(\sum_{\phi_s} \sum_{\tau} |h_{VH}(\phi_s, \tau)|^2) \quad (4)$$

where $h_{VV}(\phi_s, \tau)$ and $h_{VH}(\phi_s, \tau)$ are the steering dependent channel impulse response obtained by IFFT. The average measured XPD over the 46 Tx/Rx positions is 11.3 dB. The averaged discrimination between polarizations HV and HH can be computed in same way, and give similar results.

The accuracy of the average XPD prediction is evaluated for three different RT parameter sets, and reported in Tab.I. In *Set 1* and *Set 2*, the parameter K_{xpol} gets the value 0.5 as proposed in [12], while a lower value at 0.25 is considered in *Set 3*. The calibration parameters XPR_F and XPR_O of *Set 1* corresponds to default values available in the RT tool, which were calibrated from outdoor urban measurements in the past. On the contrary, *Set 2* and *Set 3* use neutral XPR_F and XPR_O values i.e. they do not bring any correction to original RT calculation. It is found that *Set 3* gives the best performance with an average XPD value of 12.1 dB. The mean error on the overall Tx/Rx positions, is only 0.79 dB. The results show that the diffuse scattering is largely impacting the depolarization, and that a low K_{xpol} value adjusting is needed. The reason may be that the environment contains many smooth metallic surfaces; then the diffused power is then mainly captured by the VV or HH polarizations. Fig. 4(a) represents the average channel gain and XPD for the different positions measured and compared to the calibrated RT tool. Based on these results, the *Set 3* parameters are used for the rest of the study.

TABLE I: RT Model Configuration and Evaluation

Parameter	Set 1	Set 2	Set 3
K_{xpol}	0.5	0.5	0.25
XPR_F	0.5	1	1
XPR_O [dB]	-2	0	0
Mean XPD error [dB]	-4.57	-2.56	0.76
XPD error std. dev. [dB]	2.86	2.85	2.75

B. Large Scale Parameters Evaluation

As a further step, the accuracy of the RT model is also assessed by comparing measured and predicted Large Scale Parameters (LSPs) of the quasi-monostatic backscattering

channel. For calculation of the mean delay and the delay spread, the dual-polar matrices are reduced to a Power Delay Profile (PDP) by incoherent summation of the power at constant angle of arrival. Similarly, for the calculation of mean angle and angular spread, the dual-polar matrices are reduced to a Power Angular Profile (PAP) by incoherent summation of the power at constant time of arrival. To avoid the integration of noise in the measurement domain, a threshold of -100 dB is applied on the channel responses (both measured and predicted) before calculation of LSPs. The considered LSPs include both specular and dense components.

Fig. 4: LSP comparison: measurements vs. RT predictions

Fig. 4 shows the comparison between the position-dependent predicted and measured LSPs. Tab. II and Tab. III summarize the statistics deviation of the RT prediction from measurement. The mean error in received power, delay spread and angular spread are -1.2 dB, -1.5 ns and -1.5° respectively. The standard deviation of the prediction error are 4.1 dB, 6.3 ns and 18.8° respectively. Similar performance is observed for the HH and VH polarizations and not reported here for sake of brevity.

IV. APPLICATION TO SENSING AND RADIO SLAM

A. Multi Path Component Extraction

For sensing detection applications, it is convenient to represent the channel by rays, even when estimated from measurements. At given steering angle ϕ_s , the polarimetric for the

TABLE II: LSPs Prediction Errors on VV Polarization

LSP	Statistics	Measured VV	Predicted VV
Relative power	Mean (dB)	-38.04	-39.22
	Mean error (dB)	-	-1.18
	Std. dev. error (dB)	-	4.07
Delay Spread	Mean (ns)	13.64	12.17
	Mean error (ns)	-	-1.47
	Std. dev. error (ns)	-	6.27
Angular Spread	Mean (°)	55.36	53.87
	Mean error (°)	-	-1.48
	Std. dev. error(°)	-	18.81

TABLE III: LSPs Prediction Errors on VH Polarization

LSP	Statistics	Measured VH	Predicted VH
Relative power	Mean (dB)	-50.46	-51.52
	Mean error (dB)	-	-1.06
	Std. dev. error (dB)	-	3.12
Delay Spread	Mean (ns)	12.89	9.58
	Mean error (ns)	-	-3.31
	Std. dev. error (ns)	-	4.55
Angular Spread	Mean (°)	58.48	55.71
	Mean error (°)	-	-2.76
	Std. dev. error(°)	-	13.14

(ζ, ξ) polarization combination, the impulse response can be written as:

$$h_{\zeta, \xi}(\phi_s, \tau) = \sum_{l=1}^L \alpha_l^{s, \zeta, \xi} \cdot \delta(\tau - \tau_l) \quad (5)$$

where L represents number of rays; τ_l and $\alpha_l^{s, \zeta, \xi}$ the l -th MPC delay and amplitude. In this notation we explicit the Ω_l^{AoA} Ω_l^{AoD} the angle of arrival and departure. These MPCs are extracted by a 2D-CLEAN like procedure [11], that can be summarized as follows:

- 1) Generate a Power Angular Delay Profile (PADP) by putting together the Power Delay Profiles (PDP) associated with all the steering directions ϕ_s .
- 2) Find the maximum amplitude value in the PADP, and store its value, its delay and steering angle. The MPCs $\hat{\tau}_l$ delay is obtained by a peak search, considering a bin fixed at $\Delta\tau = 2$ ns.
- 3) Apply a side lobe elimination mask centered on the angle-delay map estimated on Step 1 centered at $\hat{\tau}_l$ and $\hat{\phi}_l$ estimated in Step 2. The mask is defined taking into account the antennas gain pattern, resulting in the following condition:

$$\frac{|h_{\zeta, \xi}(\phi_s, \tau)|^2}{|h_{\zeta, \xi}(\hat{\phi}_l, \hat{\tau}_l)|^2} \leq \eta \frac{G_{\zeta}(\phi_s - \phi_l)G_{\xi}(\phi_s - \phi_l)}{G_{\zeta}(\phi_s - \phi_l)G_{\xi}(\phi_s - \phi_l)} \quad (6)$$

where $G_{\zeta}(\phi)$ and $G_{\xi}(\phi)$ represent the antenna gain pattern in ζ ξ polarization. The η factor is a constant to be adapted depending on the scenario. If the threshold is exceeded, a new MPC is searched by looking for the next maxima in the azimuth domain. The side lobe level threshold from the new peak is added and the algorithm can continue until no new peak is found.

Fig. 5: Example of PAPD and MPCs extraction by 2D-CLEAN like method: measurement (a) and simulation (b).

The result of this peak search is shown superimposed on the measured PADP in the Fig. 5. Note that the extracted MPC (or equivalent ray) is weighted considering the amplitude value estimated for each peak. This MPC estimation procedure is applied to both measured and RT simulated response. The similar results obtained validate the use of RT tool for channel estimation and detection techniques based on fine MPCs evaluation.

B. Radio SLAM

To highlight the potential of RT models as a tool for developing optimal detection approaches, a benchmark test is proposed using a SLAM algorithm based generating the reconstructed trajectory from successive predicted ‘laser scans’ [13]. The RT data, once restricted to a 2D scenario with only round-trip rays, corresponds, in a way, to an ideal Lidar scanning scenario. In this case, the rays emerging from the scattering processes account for the majority of objects detection. But when incorporating Radar constraints, for example with the data simulated with horn antenna patterns, finite frequency bandwidth and finite azimuthal scanning, the estimation resulting from this dataset will give lower resolution and the diffuse part of the channel will be more difficult

Fig. 6: Radio SLAM results: half space beam scanning (a), 360° full beam scanning (b).

to detect since individually diffuse rays contain less power. Therefore, two scenarios are considered:

- 2D scan extraction from a scan in the front half-space only, i.e. $\pm 90^\circ$, as for the measurements;
- 2D scan extraction from RT data, i.e. on $\pm 180^\circ$ without considering any constraint of the radar system.

The trajectory tested is the one shown in Fig 1. The occupancy grids obtained and estimated trajectories are shown in Fig. 6. In the case of half space beam scanning (Fig 6(a)), the trajectory as well as the map are poorly investigated. The loss of coherence between rays extracted at successive Tx/Rx positions leads to a diverging trajectory at one point but a good estimate for the initial rectilinear part of the trajectory. On the contrary when the channel is sounded by steering over the full $\pm 180^\circ$ field of view, the trajectory as well as the map are finely estimated, as shown in Fig 6(b).

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a multi-polarimetric millimeter-wave backscattering channel measurement campaign carried out in an industrial-like scenario. The measurement results and the extracted channel parameters are compared with an RT-based channel model. The RT tool exploits the accurate 3D

representation of the environment; it is calibrated from both bistatic measurements (previous work) and monostatic radar-based measurements (here considered), making it suitable for communication and sensing scenarios. The predicted channel presented a very good agreement w.r.t. experiments in terms of large scale parameters, including cross-polar discrimination. The deterministic tool has been exploited to test the performance of channel-dependent algorithms: an application of a CLEAN-like approach for the channel estimation and a SLAM technique. As an example, the results allows to estimate the performance of Radio SLAM according to the beam-steering angle capabilities of the sensing system.

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